

ICLR2023_RESNET-50_TINY_IMAGE NET_ANALYSIS

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1 NEW EXPERIMENTS AND SUMMARY

New experiments:

1. We perform pruning analysis on ResNet-50 trained on Tiny ImageNet dataset (Wu et al. (2017)). The Tiny ImageNet dataset consists of 200 classes and each class has 500 training examples and 50 validation examples.
2. Previously, we pruned only the main branch connections each having (3 x 3) filters across different stages in ResNet-50 as shown in Figure 1. Now, we also prune connections, each having (1 x 1) convolutional filters across the residual branch and the main branch in different stages of ResNet-50.
3. We compare the proposed pruning method with feature map based active filter pruning methods such as HRank (Lin et al. (2020)) and Energy-aware (Yeom et al. (2021)) pruning methods. We also use passive filter pruning methods such as entry-wise l_1 -norm (Li et al. (2017)) and entry-wise geometric median (GM) (He et al. (2019)) for comparison.
4. In addition to performing experimental analysis on ResNet-50 trained using Tiny ImageNet, we also repeat the previous steps (2) and (3) for ResNet-50 trained using CIFAR-10.

Summary:

- (i) For ResNet-50 on Tiny ImageNet as shown in Figure 2, the pruned network obtained after pruning convolutional layers with (3 x 3) filters from stage 4 and stage 5 at 25% pruning ratio results in an accuracy drop of less than 1 percentage point compared to that of the unpruned network .
- (ii) For ResNet-50 on Tiny ImageNet as shown in Figure 3(a), pruning convolutional layers with (1 x 1) filters along with (3 x 3) filters across various stages at different pruning ratios result in more drop in accuracy compared to that of pruning convolutional layers with (3 x 3) filters alone.
- (iii) On contrary, for ResNet-50 on CIFAR-10 as shown in Figure 3(b), pruning convolutional layers with (1 x 1) filters along with (3 x 3) filters across various stages at different pruning ratios result similar accuracy with ≤ 0.5 percentage point compared to that of pruning convolutional layers with (3 x 3) filters alone.
- (iv) For ResNet-50 on Tiny ImageNet dataset in Table 1, the number of parameters are reduced by 16% at less than 1 percentage points drop in accuracy compared to that of the unpruned network. At 32% reduction in parameters, the accuracy in the pruned network reduces by 1.90 percentage points compared to the unpruned network. For ResNet-50 using CIFAR-10 in Figure 3(b), we find that pruning reduces $\approx 87\%$ parameters at no loss in performance compared to that of the unpruned network.
- (v) (ii), (iii) and (iv) suggest that ResNet-50 shows more redundancy for smaller classification problem e.g. CIFAR-10 which has 10 classes and sufficient training example (5000 per class) compared to that of the Tiny ImageNet classification having 200 classes with 500 examples per class for training. Also, there is a little scope to prune (1 x 1) filters along with (3 x 3) filters compared to that of pruning only (3 x 3) filters across various stages in ResNet-50 for Tiny ImageNet dataset due to significant drop in accuracy compared to that of the unpruned network as shown in Figure 3(a).
- (vi) In contrast to the active filter pruning methods as given in Table 2 for ResNet-50 on Tiny ImageNet, we find that the proposed pruning method is 3 times faster compared to Energy-aware (Yeom et al. (2021)), 4.5 times faster compared to HRank (Lin et al. (2020)) and gives

similar performance without using any dataset in obtaining the pruned network. Similarly, for ResNet-50 on CIFAR-10, the proposed pruning method is 2 times faster compared to Energy-aware (Yeom et al. (2021)), 3 times faster compared to HRank (Lin et al. (2020)), and gives similar performance without using any dataset in obtaining a pruned network. In contrast to the existing passive filter pruning methods, the proposed pruning method achieves similar performance as shown in Figure 4.

In conclusion, the proposed pruning method is able to achieve similar performance compared to that of the existing feature map based active filter pruning methods at reduced computational time and without involving any dataset for pruning. The proposed pruning method generalises better across audio and image domains compared to the existing passive filter pruning method.

The detailed experimental analysis is explained below,

2 PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS ON RESNET-50 USING TINY IMAGENET AND CIFAR-10 DATASETS

We perform pruning analysis on Tiny ImageNet dataset using ResNet-50. We also perform some more experiments on CIFAR-10 using ResNet-50 (Previous experiments are in Appendix). Experimental setup and performance analysis is explained in the following subsections,

2.1 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Tiny ImageNet dataset: The Tiny ImageNet dataset (Wu et al. (2017)) is a subset of the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge(ILSVRC) dataset (Russakovsky et al. (2015)). The Tiny ImageNet consists of 200 different image classes. Each class has 500 training images (100,000 in total), 50 validation images (10,000 in total), and 50 test images (10,000 in total). In addition, the images are re-sized to (64x64) pixels from (256x256) pixels in standard ImageNet. We download the Tiny ImageNet dataset from (Sharma (2017)). The Tiny ImageNet dataset has labelled classes for training and validation datasets.

Unpruned network: We obtain an unpruned network by training ResNet-50 (with pre-trained ImageNet weights) on Tiny ImageNet training dataset for 300 epochs with stochastic gradient descent (SGD) optimizer and cross entropy loss function. The unpruned network has 24.16M parameters, 333M multiply-accumulate operations (MACs) per inference and achieves 55.53% accuracy similar to that obtained by (Sun (2017)) on validation dataset.

Pruning layers in ResNet-50: For pruning, we consider all convolutional layers of ResNet-50 including (1 x 1) and (3 x 3) convolutional layers across various stages as shown in Figure 1. To perform fine-tuning of the pruned network, we re-train the pruned network for 150 epochs with similar conditions such as same optimizer as used in training the unpruned network.

Other methods used for comparison: For comparison, we use passive filter pruning methods such as entry-wise l_1 -norm (Li et al. (2017)) and entry-wise geometric median (GM) (He et al. (2019)). We also compare the proposed pruning method with the feature map based active filter pruning methods including HRank (Lin et al. (2020)) and Energy-aware pruning Yeom et al. (2021).

A brief overview of the active filter pruning methods used for comparison is given below,

- **HRank:** This method opts three steps to obtain a pruned network. 1) A set of feature maps are generated for a given filter using a set of examples. 2) Rank of the feature maps is computed and an average rank computed for various examples is used as a criterion to quantify filter importance. 3) The filters with low average rank are eliminated and a fine-tuning procedure is opted to compensate the performance loss.
- **Energy-aware:** This method uses a set of input data to generate feature maps for a given convolutional layer and then compute energy of each feature map by computing nuclear norm (sum of all singular values) of each feature map. A feature map with low energy is pruned and then fine-tuning of the pruned network is performed.

Figure 1: (a) Architecture to classify Tiny ImageNet dataset using ResNet-50 (stage 1 to stage 5) which comprises of (b) identity blocks and (c) convolutional blocks, followed by global average pooling layer, a dense and a classification layer. “BN” denotes batch normalization. “ReLU” denotes rectified linear unit activation function and Conv2D is a convolutional layer with 2D filters.

To perform feature map based active filter pruning, we generate feature maps using randomly selected 500 examples from the training dataset, and apply HRank and Energy-aware pruning algorithm to compute filter importance.

2.2 PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Figure 2: Accuracy obtained for Tiny ImageNet dataset on ResNet-50 after pruning each (3 x 3) convolutional layers across various stages at different pruning ratio.

Figure 2 shows accuracy obtained using pruned ResNet-50 obtained after pruning (3 x 3) convolutional layers across various stages at different pruning ratios in ResNet-50. At 25% pruning ratio, the accuracy drop is approximately 2 percentage points compared to that of the unpruned network. For stage 4 and stage 5, the accuracy drop is less than 1 percentage points compared to that of the

unpruned network. In general, accuracy drop increases either by pruning more number of stages or by increasing pruning ratio per layer.

Figure 3: Accuracy obtained after pruning convolutional layers from stage 4 and stage 5 in ResNet-50 for Tiny ImageNet and CIFAR-10 dataset.

Figure 3 compares the accuracy obtained after pruning convolutional layers with (3 x 3) filters in the main branch and residual branch across stage 4 and stage 5 of ResNet-50 for Tiny ImageNet and CIFAR-10 datasets. For Tiny ImageNet as shown in Figure 3(a), the accuracy obtained after pruning (1 x 1) convolutional layers along with (3 x 3) convolutional layers is less than that of pruning (3 x 3) convolutional layers alone. On the other hand, we obtain similar accuracy for CIFAR-10 dataset. This suggests that the ResNet-50 shows more redundancy for smaller classification problems with 10 classes having sufficient training examples (5000 per class) compared to that of the relatively difficult classification problem with 200 classes with 500 training examples per class.

Next, Table 1 compares the accuracy, MACs and parameters in the unpruned network with that of the pruned network (a, c, e) having important filters obtained using the proposed pruning method as an initialisation before fine-tuning process, (b, d, f) the same pruned network as obtained in (a, c, e) and trained from scratch with random initialization. The parameters and the MACs are reduced by 10% and 16% respectively with an accuracy drop $\leq 1\%$ compared to that of the unpruned network. On the other hand, the parameters are reduced by 32% and the MACs are reduced by 21% at 1.9 percentage points drop in accuracy compared to that of the unpruned network. The accuracy of the pruned network obtained from the proposed pruning method is better than the same pruned network trained from scratch.

Table 1: Comparison of accuracy, the MACs and the parameters among the unpruned network, the pruned networks (a, c, f) obtained using the proposed pruning method and the same pruned networks obtained in (a, c, f), however, trained from scratch (b, d, e).

Network	Accuracy (%)	MACs	Reduced MACs	Parameters	Reduced parameters
ResNet-50 on Tiny ImageNet	55.53	333M	-	24.16M	-
(a) Pruned ResNet-50 on Tiny ImageNet ($p=25\%$, Stage 4 to 5)	54.72	298M	10%	20.33M	16%
(b) Pruned ResNet-50 on Tiny ImageNet ((a) - scratch)	23.70	—"	—"	—"	—"
(c) Pruned ResNet-50 on Tiny ImageNet ($p = 25\%$, stage 3 to 5)	54.20	285M	15%	20.11M	17%
(d) Pruned ResNet-50 on Tiny ImageNet ((c) - scratch)	23.51	—"	—"	—"	—"
(e) Pruned ResNet-50 on Tiny ImageNet ($p = 50\%$, stage 3 to 5)	53.63	264M	21%	16.49M	32%
(f) Pruned ResNet-50 on Tiny ImageNet ((e) - scratch)	23.30	—"	—"	—"	—"

Comparison with other methods: The proposed pruning method gives similar or marginally better performance (0.20 to 0.50 percentage point) compared to that of the existing passive filter pruning methods as shown in Figure 4. Table 2 compares the accuracy, pruning time at same pruning conditions (same pruned architecture) obtained using the proposed pruning method with that of the active filter pruning methods such as HRank and Energy-aware for ResNet-50 on Tiny ImageNet and CIFAR-10 datasets. We find that the proposed filter pruning method gives similar accuracy

Table 2: Comparison of accuracy, the MACs, the parameters and pruning time of the proposed operator norm based pruning method with existing feature map based pruning methods such as HRank and Energy aware for ResNet-50 on Tiny ImageNet and CIFAR-10 dataset. The pruning time is a local time duration between the start and end of the pruning algorithm in computing the filter importance for all layers in the unpruned network. The pruning time is computed using python time method `time.asctime()`.

Network	Pruning Method	Data used in Pruning	Pruning Time (mins)	FT	Accuracy (%)	Parameters	MACs
ResNet-50 on Tiny ImageNet (Input: $64 \times 64 \times 3$)	No pruning (Baseline)	-	-	-	55.53	24.16M	333M
	HRank (Lin et al. (2020))	✓	9.11	✓	54.82	20.32M	298M
	Energy-aware pruning (Yeom et al. (2021))	✓	6.06	✓	54.60	20.32M	298M
	Ours	×	1.53	✓	54.70	20.32M	298M
ResNet-50 on CIFAR-10 (Input: $32 \times 32 \times 3$)	No pruning (Baseline)	-	-	-	83.37	24.11M	99M
	HRank (Lin et al. (2020))	✓	6.30	✓	83.60	3.12M	39M
	Energy-aware pruning (Yeom et al. (2021))	✓	4.33	✓	83.43	3.12M	39M
	Ours	×	1.53	✓	83.44	3.12M	39M

Figure 4: Convergence plot during fine-tuning of the pruned ResNet-50 for Tiny ImageNet at different pruning ratio.

without using any dataset in pruning. Also, the computational time in obtaining pruned architecture is at least 2 times less than that of the active filter pruning methods.

3 SUMMARY

In conclusion, the proposed pruning method is able to achieve similar performance compared to that of the existing feature map based active filter pruning methods without involving any dataset at reduced computational time in pruning as well. The proposed pruning method generalises better across audio and image domains compared to that of the existing passive filter pruning method.

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